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Corrosion and nanomechanical properties of Mo–coordinated chitosan coatings on Mg alloy WE43

Dzmitry S. Kharytonau^{1,2}, Ewelina Jarek², Konrad Skowron^{1,2}, Małgorzata Zimowska³, Illia Dobryden⁴, Nils Almqvist⁵

- (1) *Electrochemistry and Corrosion Laboratory, Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry, Polish Academy of Sciences, 30–239 Krakow, Poland*
- (2) *Soft Matter Nanostructures, Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry, Polish Academy of Sciences, 30–239 Krakow, Poland*
- (3) *Heterogeneous catalysis: theory and experiment, Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry, Polish Academy of Sciences, 30–239 Krakow, Poland*
- (4) *Rise Research Institutes of Sweden, 114 28 Stockholm, Sweden*
- (5) *Division of Materials Science, Department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics, Luleå University of Technology, 971–87 Luleå, Sweden*

Electrophoretic deposition is a commonly used technique to obtain chitosan–based functional coatings on various surfaces. Biodegradable materials are one of the possible application areas of such coatings. In particular, they can be used as a carrier of drugs or antibacterial materials or to control the degradation rate of temporary implant materials. At the same time, to control the degradation rate of the chitosan coating itself, it can be modified with corrosion inhibitors. In this regard, implementation of coordinated co–deposition of chitosan with molybdate ions seems to be a perspective strategy to increase the corrosion resistance of chitosan films. The aim of this work was to develop chitosan coatings coordinated with molybdate ions via electrophoretic deposition on the WE43 magnesium alloy.

The coatings were obtained by the cathodic deposition technique using the medium molecular weight chitosan solutions (8 g/L of chitosan, 1% acetic acid), containing 50 or 80 vol.% of ethanol. To obtain Mo–coordinated coatings, different amounts of sodium molybdate were added to the solutions. As–deposited coatings were characterized by Fourier–transform infrared spectroscopy and X–ray diffraction. The morphology of the coatings was examined by scanning electron microscopy. Corrosion performance of the coatings in the initial stages of degradation in Hank's solution was examined by dynamic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The nanomechanical properties of the coatings were examined by multifrequency Intermodulation AFM (ImAFM) spectroscopy. The results of the measurements confirmed that uniform chitosan coatings were deposited on the surface in all examined conditions. Corrosion experiments showed that the best corrosion performance was reached for coatings deposited from the solutions containing 80 vol% of ethanol and 3 mM of the added molybdate ions. The ImAFM results confirmed higher values of effective elastic modulus of the formed Mo–coordinated coatings comparing to pure chitosan coatings deposited in the same conditions.

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